

The Adaptable Post

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We are all familiar with the pressures facing most posts in the last few years, including a steep decline in mail volume and increased competition. In mechanized operations, volume has often dropped faster than machines and labor can be taken out. Posts need to come up with an operating strategy that is adapted to these new mail patterns, including new approaches to distribution and operating plans.

Industrialized posts have developed highly automated technologies to read addresses, and sort and sequence letters and even small packets. Operating plans provide the underlying discipline required to leverage the benefits of automation, and distribute and deliver the mail efficiently. Processing areas are defined, transport schedules are established, and deadlines for processing mail are set. These operating schedules are refined over time, but they remain essentially static and are changed infrequently. Labor schedules are often established based on these static operating plans.

Today, excess labor and infrastructure associated with these

static plans are erasing some of the productivity gains achieved through automation in the last thirty years.

Inventory is our friend

Every day, these static operating plans push items through the same time definite paths, consolidating mail through the same plants, using the same primary sort programs, towards the same delivery preparation and final delivery processes. When one examines the mail in each stream, one often finds faster mail, such as first class mail in the U.S. co-mingled with slower mail, like U.S. standard mail, being processed in the same time windows, and at the same speed. The proportion of slower class mail being hurried to its destination faster than necessary is increasing, as the proportion of faster first class mail keeps dropping.

The additional amount of time available to deliver standard mail, and sometimes the additional time also available to deliver first class, could be used to perform a number of cost saving actions. For instance, delivery may be avoided to certain points on certain days, facilities may be bypassed on certain days, or transport may be combined. Actions may include holding and consolidating mail, or bypassing and rerouting mail to forego processing, or transport, and thereby create larger, more economical batches. The main idea is to use information about mail and its characteristics to create an adaptable operations environment

that can take advantage of available information and time and generate more cost effective routings.

In the rest of this article, we examine some of these possible actions in the context of ‘the adaptable post:’

- Dynamic network management: how mail flows can be managed in near real time.
- Delivery point economics: how delivery operations can be controlled together as a function of volumes and service standards.

- Yield management: the ability to work with mailers to take advantage, like the airlines, of available capacity.
- Advanced labor management: crew scheduling.

Dynamic network management

The main concept is to deliberately take advantage of the time available to deliver each mail piece. This means that the normal mail processing operations cycle does not apply automatically to each piece of mail,

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and that a piece of mail may be held or diverted based on a number of factors. For instance, some mail inducted on Monday may be held in inventory along the way to form larger batches, provided that service commitments are respected. Sort programs on automated equipment would adapt from one day to another, driving mail through one facility instead of another. Transport will also be affected since mail will follow different paths across the network on its way to its destination mailbox.

Different degrees of flexibility can be built into an operating environment, and the system can be designed to react at different speeds. At first, opportunities to adapt from the daily schedule can be implemented on a repeatable weekly or monthly basis. Sort schemes and transport schedules can be made to change predictably from one day to another because of weekly or seasonal patterns. A post can then graduate to a more dynamic level of adaptation, for instance when information about large mailings is integrated into oper-

ating plans in near real time. Sort schemes and transport are then adapted based on overall processing costs. The operating plans find ways to leverage network wide transport and processing capacity, aiming to maximize the operating efficiency of each plant in the network, and the transportation utilization on each route between plants.

Delivery point economics

Delivery point economics uses the same concept: short term delivery planning applications use detailed information about the mail pipeline to create opportunities to reduce delivery costs. Mail can be held in the network, or at delivery units, when distribution economics suggest and service standards permit, so that delivery routes can be shortened, skipped, or combined.

A similar concept is being tested in France by La Poste, where mail carriers collaborate to manage delivery routes on a daily basis based on the availability of personnel and the volume of mail to be distributed. Finnish Post has gone further, emailing scans of physical mail pieces to rural customers, then optimizing rural deliveries of the physical pieces every other week. The objective is to leverage both mail delivery capacity and the time available to deliver each piece to create heavier delivery density and lower delivery costs per piece.

Yield management

The concept of yield management was introduced by American Airlines

in 1985. Yield management is the process of understanding, anticipating and influencing consumer behavior in order to maximize yield or profits from a fixed, perishable resource. For posts, the perishable resource is the processing and delivery capacity of the network on a given day. On some days of the week, during some months of the year, there is additional capacity because overall mail volume is lower. During or prior to holidays, available capacity may be reduced, and operators rely on more expensive overtime.

Using its capacity to anticipate mail volumes on a future given day, the postal operator would price its available capacity to mailers accordingly, and invite them to take advantage of this capacity. On low volume days, prices offered to mailers for advertising mail would go down to reflect the availability of processing capacity. During high volume periods, prices for advertising mail would go up to reflect the scarcity of capacity available. Mailers could reserve processing and delivery capacity ahead of time at pre-agreed prices, thus commirring to stable and predictable mail flows.

Advanced labor management

Traditionally, postal operations were made predictable by setting fixed labor schedules and rules that enabled postal managers to line up predictable human resources. Today, modern enterprises must tailor their human resources more precisely to the demands of their operations, and to assign the appropriate

level of labor to meet the expected workload.

Airlines and rail companies have learned to assign the right level of labor to the expected operational workload through crew scheduling. Under crew scheduling, qualified workers bid for specific tours or combinations of work shifts offered by the company using a sophisticated software application that takes into account seniority, skill levels, locations where the work needs to be performed, and labor agreements. Some programs even take into account pairing of experienced workers with more junior members to come up with balanced work teams. Labor rules at posts may have to be adjusted before crew scheduling can be implemented, but airlines and railroads have shown that this can be done in a union environment.

Next steps

Industrialized posts have done an amazing job of developing and introducing automation in the last thirty years. Now, another revolution is needed to extend these productivity gains and further reduce costs and increase performance: leveraging information about the mail stream to find better and more cost effective ways to route mail through the network, every day. To move forward with the concept of the adaptable post, operators should consider the following steps:

- Examine, describe and evaluate key internal capabilities and processes to determine how adaptable they are. These include

engineering, network and operations planning, network management, marketing and sales, labor and facilities management.

- Establish an internal measure of adaptability by identifying various operational features and capabilities and periodically reporting on progress.
- Outline an advanced operations management strategy which incorporates adaptability, and develop an internal white paper to communicate the concept and roadmap.
- Create a community of interest within the post to discuss projects, initiatives and best prac-

tices. Organize visits and discussions with other posts.

- Outline and fund a number of initiatives to gradually increase the degree of adaptability, and measure and report on progress.
- Appoint an executive to take the lead in enabling the transformation, with the authority and the manpower to execute the change.

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